

Who sees homœopaths?

A study of patient characteristics in a homœopathic family practice

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Introduction

The practice of homœopathic medicine is becoming more common in the United States, Europe, Latin America and Asia. In the US, homœopathic medicines, which are approved and regulated by the Federal Drug Administration, have undergone a 1,000% increase in sales in the past ten years.

As more patients seek non-conventional types of treatment such as homœopathy, it becomes important to look at the characteristics of patients seeking such treatment and the conditions for which they seek care. In this study, we compared the demographic and diagnostic characteristics of homœopathic patients with those seeing a conventional general or family practitioner to identify differences between the two groups.

Methods

Information on approximately 2,500 patients seen over the five year period from January 1984 to December 1988 in a homœopathic family practice in Seattle, Washington, USA, was collected and compared with results from the National Ambulatory Medical Care Survey (NAMCS) of general and family practitioners for the period of January 1980 to December 1981.

TABLE 1. *Age and sex characteristics. Patients in a homœopathic practice compared to the National Ambulatory Medical Care Survey*

Sex	% Female		% Male		
Homœopathic	60.7		39.3		
NAMCS	60.1		39.9		
Age (per cent)	0-14	15-24	25-44	45-64	65+
Homœopathic	30.3	6.5	45	14.2	4
NAMCS	19.5	16.6	30	19.1	14.9

Results

The sex distribution of patients in the homœopathic practice was similar to that found in the national sample (Table 1). For the homœopathic sample, 60.7% of patients were female and 39.3% male, which is almost identical to the sex distribution from the NAMCS.

The homœopathic patient population can be seen to be considerably younger than that of the NAMCS physicians (Table 1), even when the same age group of physicians, 35-44 years old, is compared. The homœopaths saw more children and young adults between the ages of 25-44 years old, while the NAMCS physicians were more likely to see patients in the two older age groups.

The most common diagnoses in the two

TABLE 2. *Most common diagnoses, homœopathic and National Ambulatory Medical Care Survey physicians*

	% cases
Homœopathic physicians	
Allergic rhinitis	6.3
Unexplained fatigue	5.5
Headaches	5.5
Neurotic disorders	5.5
Dermatitis	5.2
Otitis media	3.4
Upper respiratory infection	3.2
Premenstrual syndrome	2.5
Functional bowel syndrome	2.5
Asthma	2.3
NAMCS physicians	
General exam/prenatal/well-baby	8.1
Essential hypertension	7.5
Upper respiratory infection	3.9
Diabetes mellitus	2.7
Obesity	2.3
Acute pharyngitis	2.3
Bronchitis	1.8
Otitis media	1.7
Neurotic disorders	1.2
Chronic sinusitis	1.2

TABLE 3. Diagnostic categories homœopathic practice and National Ambulatory Medical Care Survey

Category	Homœopathic	NAMCS
Infections	3.7	3.4
Neoplasms	1.0	1.2
Endocrine	2.5	4.1
Mental	7.2	2.3
Nervous/sensory	6.8	6.2
Circulatory	3.1	10.0
Respiratory	16.2	18.0
Digestive	7.6	4.7
Genitourinary	10.5	6.5
Skin	9.2	4.5
Musculo-skel.	4.2	6.8
Ill-defined symptoms/signs	19.5	4.0
Injury/poison	2.6	9.7
Supplemental*	1.2	16.6

*Includes general exams, prenatal care, well-baby, and post-operative care.

groups can be seen in Table 2. In the homœopathic practice, the most common diagnoses were allergies, unexplained fatigue, headaches, dermatitis, neurotic disorders, otitis media and upper respiratory infection. This differed from the national sample, where the most common initial visits were for essential hypertension, upper respiratory infection, diabetes mellitus, obesity, acute pharyngitis, bronchitis and otitis media.

Table 3 shows the proportions of patients seen by diagnostic categories between the two groups, adjusted for age and geographic location

of the physician. The largest differences can be seen in the disease categories of circulatory system, genitourinary system, mental illness, ill-defined symptoms and signs, and 'supplementary' classification.

Discussion

The diagnostic data indicate that homœopaths are more likely to be consulted for chronic illnesses, while the typical US general/family practitioner is seen more for routine examinations and acute illnesses. This suggests that homœopaths may be consulted for cases refractory to conventional treatment, rather than as the initial provider. It also appears that people with illnesses for which there is a known effective treatment, such as hypertension, diabetes mellitus, and injuries or poisoning, are more likely to go to a standard practitioner, while those with psychological and/or ill-defined signs and symptoms for which conventional treatment is less successful are more often found in a homœopathic practice. Of interest is the high percentage of homœopathic patients seen for otitis media, which could suggest that standard treatment of otitis media is sometimes unsatisfactory.

This study suggests that the current role of homœopathic treatment in the health care system may be for chronic and ill-defined disorders that are not easily managed by existing standard medical treatment. Further studies of the effectiveness of this form of treatment as well as a comparison of its cost to that of standard treatment would seem appropriate.

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